

Evaluation of an urban stream restoration project through water quality analysis and survey of the neighbourhood residents

Évaluation d'un projet de restauration d'un petit fleuve urbaine à travers du suivi de la qualité de l'eau et d'entretien avec les habitants locaux

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RÉSUMÉ

Cette recherche s'inscrit dans le cadre du projet SWITCH (Sustainable Water Management Improves Tomorrow's Cities' Health). Ce projet est coordonné par l'UNESCO et se compose d'un réseau de 32 institutions, parmi lesquelles se trouvent la mairie de Belo Horizonte (PBH) et l'Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (UFMG). Parmi les actions conduites par PBH dans le cadre du projet SWITCH, on distingue le programme Drenurbs dont le principal objectif est la restauration et la salubrité de l'environnement des fonds de vallées de la municipalité. Compte tenu de l'importance d'évaluer les interventions de restauration des cours d'eau proposés par le Drenurbs, l'objectif général de cet article est d'évaluer l'effectivité du projet de restauration du petit fleuve Baléares, dans la ville de Belo Horizonte. Les outils d'évaluation utilisés sont: (i) la vérification de la qualité hydrique (paramètres physiques et chimiques); (ii) enquête auprès de la population du bassin hydrographique. L'évaluation de la qualité hydrique a été effectuée en deux temps : pré-restauration (septembre 2003 – novembre 2006) et post-restauration (février 2008 – février 2009). L'enquête auprès des habitants a été menée en octobre 2008 seulement. Les résultats sur la qualité hydrique montrent une amélioration significative dans tous les paramètres évalués après la période post-restauration. Ils montrent également un changement dans le mode de pollution entre les périodes étudiées. L'enquête auprès des habitants démontre que les résultats de l'intervention ont été bien acceptés par la population, apportant ainsi de bonnes perspectives quant à la réalisation de projets du même type dans d'autres bassins versants urbains. Cependant, la préférence de la population va toujours vers la canalisation des cours d'eau. Ces résultats pourraient permettre de financer les futures évaluations des interventions réalisées par le Drenurbs dans le petit fleuve Baléares.

ABSTRACT

This research is part of the SWITCH Project (Sustainable Water Management Improves Tomorrow's Cities' Health), which is coordinated by UNESCO and constitutes of a 32 institutions working net. Among these institutions are the Belo Horizonte Government (PBH) and Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (UFMG). One of the interventions conducted by PBH is the Drenurbs Program that aims at the restoration and environmental sanitation of municipal watersheds. Considering the importance of assessing the stream restoration interventions proposed by Drenurbs, the main objective of this paper is to assess the effectiveness of the results obtained by the Baleares creek restoration project in Belo Horizonte. The following assessment tools were used: (i) monitoring of water quality (physical and chemical parameters); and (ii) survey with the population in the watershed. Tools (i) were assessed in two distinct periods: pre-restoration (September 2003-November 2006) and post-restoration (February 2008- February 2009). The survey was done once in October 2008. The water quality results revealed a significant improvement in all assessed parameters between pre restoration and post restorations periods, besides a change in the patterns of the average seasonal concentrations of the monitored indicators. The survey indicated that the results of the intervention were well accepted by the population, with good perspectives in relation to the deployment of similar projects in other urban watersheds. However, the preference for a "sanitary avenue" is still relevant. The results could subsidize future assessments of the interventions realized by the Drenurbs in Baleares creek.

KEYWORDS

Monitoring of Water Quality, Popular Perception, Baleares Creek, Drenurbs Program, Belo Horizonte.

1 INTRODUCTION

This research is part of the actions enrolled by project SWITCH – Sustainable Water Management Improves Tomorrow's Cities' Health, which is headed by UNESCO's IHE (Institute for Water Education, located in Delft, Netherlands) and composed by a network of 32 institutions, distributed in 15 countries, to which belong the Government of Belo Horizonte (PBH) and the Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (UFMG). Within the actions under the responsibility of the PBH, the Drenurbs program stands out, deserving special attention. This program is focused on creek restoration in Belo Horizonte as a way to improve sanitation and environmental quality and by this promoting the improvement of life quality in the city. The program involves not only the restoration of polluted creeks, but their complete sanitation, risk management (risk of flooding, risk to public health), erosion control at the catchment and river bed, and a housing program addressed to people living in risky areas (improvement of housing conditions, removing people from risky areas) (PBH, 2003). Under this perspective, the Drenurbs applies structural and urban interventions, along with environmental education initiatives, on the intra-urban watersheds of Belo Horizonte's territory.

Even though the restoration of stream's natural ecological conditions is not one the objectives of the Drenurbs, the design of some interventions allows this goal to be reached. This is the case of the Baleares creek, in Belo Horizonte, Brazil (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Baleares Creek

The UK Ecological Restoration Society defines restoration as the intentional process of change of one location to its natural/original form. The target is to simulate the structure, function, diversity and dynamics of a particular ecosystem, according to its historical characteristics (Riley, 1998). However, revisiting the river's original form, in many cases, is impossible (Wade *et al.*, 1998). In fact, when this type of intervention is presented, it is most commonly drawn to small watershed areas (Brown, 2000), like the ones observed in Belo Horizonte, as a recent approach of study in Brazil.

Projects for restoration of water courses are becoming more numerous, however, they are rarely subjected to post-intervention systematic evaluation programs (Kondolf & Micheli, 1995; Brown, 2000; Purcell *et al.*, 2002; Davis *et al.*, 2003). Thus, the mistakes and successes are not measured, and there is no progress in the field of urban stream restoration (Kondolf & Micheli, 1995; Purcell *et al.*, 2002).

In this context, the objectives of this paper are evaluating the results of urban stream restoration program through water quality monitoring (with physical and chemical parameters) from the impacted situation (pre-restoration) to the current situation (post-restoration); and the survey with the neighbourhood residents of Baleares creek.

2 METHODS

The restoration work has developing between 2007 and 2008. This work was split into Five reaches (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Baleares Creek Restoration Reaches.

The talweg of the first reach was deflected because a construction of a lateral street. The new talweg was covered by a rock structure, it gave stability to talweg and banks. Furthermore, it provided roughness and permeability. The banks were recomposed with grass, bushes and young trees. Sewage network was constructed. In the second reach the creek was maintained in its original position, however, its was covered by a rock structure too. The left bank had stabilized with geotextile

and bushes species. Streets and sewage network were implanted too. The reach three belongs to Baleares park area where the talweg and floodplain were maintained in natural state, and riparian vegetation was restored. In the both sides of the bankfull width were constructed streambank contetions. Other lateral street, sewage network and a small bridge for walkers. Inside the park, the riparian vegetation was restored too. The fourth reach is a small tributary of Baleares creek. It was all covered by a street with sewage network. There was not ecomorphological or landscaping intervention. The last one (reach five) is headwater areas outside the Baleares park and it is closed to public visitation. The riparian vegetation was restored and the area is still permeable

The methodological procedures here used to assessment the restoration project were based on tools selected according to international literature on evaluation of urban stream restoration programs: (i) monitoring of water quality (Charbonneau & Resh, 1992; Gumiero *et al.*, 1998; Davis *et al.*, 2003) and (ii) survey of the neighbourhood residents (Learned *et al.*, 2002; Purcell *et al.*, 2002; Purcell, 2004).

Since 2003, several field campaigns of water quality monitoring in the Baleares creek have occurred, assuming that the stream belong to the headwaters of the Velhas river watershed. This is an initiative of the Projeto Manuelzão/UFMG and the Laboratório de Ecologia de Bentos (ICB/UFMG) and has been developed in the Transdisciplinary and Transinstitucional Nucleous for das Velhas River Revitalization (NUVELHAS). Every three months, samples of water are collected for physical-chemical, analysis. The collections are equally distributed on the hydrological year, with two campaigns during the dry period (May-September) and two in the wet season (October-April). It should be noted that the studied period corresponds to the stage from September 2003 to November 2006 (pre-restoration, n=12), and from February 2008 to February 2009 (post-restoration, n=5).

In relation to the survey, 179 structured questionnaires were applied along the Baleares creek catchment and were apply in October 2008, on the post-restoration period. The procedures accomplished to execute this survey were divided in Five stages: (i) construction of geodatabank; (ii) definition of the total population and the size of sample, through the Brazilian census data; (iii) arrangement the survey form; (iv) direct application of the survey forms in the homes that were defined by sample designed and (v) results interpretation.

The census data explained that Baleares creek population is approximately 5.000 inhabitants, but only. In this case, data were provided by the IBGE in digital spreadsheets referring to the census geographic sectors (IBGE, 2002). This areas are delimited considering the political limits and not the drainage basins, it was considered the census data proportionally the area of the sector inside of each drainage basin (Goodchild & Lam, 1980; Flowerdew & Green, 1994; Macedo & Magalhães Jr, 2007; Saporito *et al.*, 2007)

The sample size was defined using the relationship between the population size and the acceptable sample error in the confidence interval of 95%, defined by statistical expression below:

$$n = \frac{N * p * q}{[(N - 1) * D + p * q]}$$

In this expression, n is the sample size, N is the population size, D is the square error limit divided by 4, p= ½, e q= 1-p (Bolfarine & Bussab, 2005). Considering the error around 7%, were applied 179 forms in all the Baleares creek catchment

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Water Quality Monitoring

The results show an enhancement in the water quality after the post-restoration period. The average concentration of dissolved oxygen (DO) was noticed, as well as the decreasing in the average concentrations of total nitrogen, total phosphorus and electrical conductivity (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Results of water quality monitoring

The considerable enhancements of the DO, total nitrogen, total phosphorus were also reached by Ruley & Rush (2002), when they describe the situation of the restoration and withdrawal of the sewage in the City Park lake, in Baton Rouge, Louisiana (USA). Colangelo (2007), on the context of the river Kissimmee's restoration (Florida, USA) also found a considerable enhancement in the average concentrations of the DO. Reductions on the total phosphorus were also found by Charbonneau & Resh (1992) while evaluating the urban stream restoration project of Strawberry creek, in Berkeley, California (USA). In relation to the electric conductivity, in Brazil, values above 100 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ denote freshwater pollution associated to urbanized areas (Cetesb, 2005). In this case, the Balears creek waters would difficultly present low values for the electric conductivity, due to its diffuse pollution

sources in runoff (Dunne & Leopold, 1978; von Sperling, 1995). However, after restoration, a decrease is observed on the collected values.

Another change occurred in the behaviour of the seasonal average values in the analysed parameters. In that sense, it is noticed on the pre-restoration period that the average concentrations of DO are superior in the wet period than in the dry period, due to the dilution of the effluents by the runoff. Likewise, the concentrations of the total nitrogen and total phosphorus, as well as the values of electrical conductivity are smaller in the wet period than in the dry one. The studies made in areas which the main agent is the punctual pollution caused by urban effluents also present similar results: Lopes *et al.* (2008), when they analysed the urban effluent of the city of Carrancas (Minas Gerais) over the homonymous creek, in relation to the DO; Maillard & Pinheiro-Santos (2008) in the talveg of Velhas river, severely impacted by the effluents of the Metropolitan Region of Belo Horizonte (RMBH) in relation to the total phosphorus and total nitrogen; and the studies Daniel *et al.* (2001) on the basin of Piracicaba river (São Paulo) and Dias *et al.* (2008), on São Pedro creek, in Juiz de Fora (Minas Gerais), in relation to the electrical conductivity.

In the post-restoration period, a change in the patterns is observed: average concentrations of DO superior to the wet period, and values to total nitrogen, total phosphorus and electrical conductivity are bigger than in the wet period. This new pattern demonstrates that there is a change in the main source of pollution in the catchment: the diffuse pollution present in the runoff has a bigger negative impact in the wet season, due to the increase in the load of elements that are potentially eutrophic (Esteves, 1998). Studies in urbanized areas, in which there are absence of effluent thrown in the water courses, also present indicative values of bigger pollution in the wet season (Lee & Bang, 2000; Pesce & Wunderlin, 2000; Daniel *et al.*, 2001; Colangelo, 2007).

3.2 Survey

It is of great importance that the urban stream restoration program also includes the neighbours in all the phases of the process, since the conception, implantation, managing and monitoring (Riley, 1998; Booth *et al.*, 2004).

An important goal of such a program is the incorporation of a new sense of identity between the neighbour dwellers and the watercourse (Palmer *et al.*, 2007). In this sense the results of the survey (Table 1) trace an opinion profile and the participation of the population directly involved with the Baleares creek.

The survey results are an important tool. In broad terms, the best way of living with the river is to integrate it to the urban space. Porath (2004) shows that the majority of the urban rivers in Brazil and in the world present anthropical modifications, and that the preservation of the valley bottoms with the creation of parks, flood control and the valorisation of the river by fluvial tourism are solutions for a river to be valorised and integrated to the urban landscape. The solutions proposed for Baleares creek correspond to that perspective. According with the survey, the park creation (and the maintenance of the wet zone) were well accepted by the population, as it contemplates the dwellers, necessities. The valorisation of the space motivates people to preserve this new conjuncture, as proposes Souza (2006). This is reinforced by the survey results, which shows that the intention of frequenting it is a good indicator of the acceptance to the interventions by the population.

The preference for the canalising and implantation of the avenue is still a reflex of the traditional conception employed in Brazil. Besides the fact that the enhanced transport system not necessarily avoids the maintenance of the valley bottom in the natural river's bed, the main model used in Brazil only canalises the watercourse, without worrying to set the interceptors. Thus, the creek is only hidden, solving only the apparent problem (Nascimento *et al.*, 1999; Porath, 2004). In relation to the Baleares creek, the greatest part of the population prefers the avenue, which is a concept based on mistaken or distorted perceptions. In that, the education measures developed in Baxter creek presented good results, as they changed mistaken perceptions that people had in relation to the creek (Purcell *et al.*, 2002; Purcell, 2004). According with this perspective, in the second assessment made in that creek, the satisfaction level, in relation to the interventions, had grown from 84% to 95% (Purcell, 2004).

Questions	Responses	
You have been informed about the restoration program?	Yes: 76% (132/172)	No: 24% (40/172)
How was it informed?	Neighbors: 46% (80/172) Government functionary: 7% (12/172)	Media and flyers: 23% (40/172) Planning assemble: 7% (12/40)
Once informed, you were asked to planning of the restoration?	Yes: 31% (41/132)	No: 69% (91/132)
Do you go to or want to attend the park?	Yes: 61% (106/172)	No: 29% (65/172)
Would you rather the total cover of creek?	Yes: 50% (86/172)	No: 50% (86/172)
Why?	Car access improve: 44% (38/86) Protect the creek of the pollution: 14% (12/86) Cover the creek: 8% (7/86) Flood Control: 4% (3/86)	Reduce sickness vectors: 19% (17/86) It more aesthetic attractive: 10% (9/86) Knew only the canalization: 8% (7/86) The park will be dangerous: 4% (3/86)
The restoration exceeded your expectations?	Yes: 78% (135/172)	No: 32% (37/172)
Why?	Water quality improve: 55% (74/135) Reduce sickness vectors: 29% (39/135) Car access improve: 19% (26/135) Flood control: 5% (7/135)	Aesthetics improve: 49% (66/135) Create the park: 25% (34/135) Remove the slum: 14% (19/135) The restoration is finish: 3% (4/135)

Table 1: Survey results

It is worth saying that the survey showed that the majority of people were informed about the restoration program by neighbours. In terms of popular participation, that exchange between the target-population and a public policy is extremely positive and important, as it enables the discussion about the actions (Souza, 2006). It is also noticed that in Brazil there is a difference in relation to the USA, where the advertisement corresponded to 80% of the way people were informed about the interventions in the Baxter creek (Purcell et al., 2002). The high satisfaction in relation to the restoration works was observed in the studies of Purcell et al., (2002) e Larned et al. (2002). Those studies call attention to the fact that expectations were overcome by the quality of the environment itself, as in the example of the Balears creek.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The water quality monitoring results show a significant improvement in the evaluated parameters between the pre-restoration and the post-restoration periods. Another interesting result was the change in the patterns of the average seasonal concentrations of the monitored indicators. In the great majority of them, a seasonal pattern inversion was observed, indicating a change in the sources of punctual pollutions to diffuse ones, as the ones observed nowadays in developed countries .

In relation to the survey, it can be concluded that the results of the interventions were well accepted by the population, what brings good perspectives to the implantation and maintenance processes of this kind of urban creeks restoration programs. However, the sanitary avenue is yet an icon that is appreciated in the urban landscape, and that, somehow, may inhibit the access to the popular participation in similar processes.

It should be considered that interventions and the general improvement in the water quality do not mean necessarily that the population will start to see the creek again as a watercourse in a short term

period, as it has always been seen as an “open-air sewage”. Besides the fact that the enhancement in the water quality is perceptible and presented in the survey, only in a medium or long term periods the population will see that flow as a water course. Only the evolution and stabilization of the fluvial system, as it was mentioned in the literature presented in this paper, could actually change the population’s perception about Baleares creek.

In the Brazilian and Latin American contexts, it is not possible to improve the fluvial environments without working on sanitary actions (collection and treatment of garbage and sewage). Restoration programs to the conjuncture in which the Baleares creek is inserted, have to be based on sanitary action, so that in a future moment, the watercourse may acquire new balance conditions. Under this perspective, the simple withdrawal of the sewage produced a quick and meaningful enhancement in the water quality. It is recommended, in future studies, to investigate how this water improvement reflects in other aspects, like health, education and valorisation of the urban space.

Besides allowing the understanding of the processes involved in the urban stream restoration practices, the evaluation of this type of intervention has great importance in the progress of a still incipient field of study in Brazil and in South-American countries.

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